
**ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE
COLLECTABILITY OF IMPORT CUSTOMS DUTIES****Maxmudov Aminjon Azimovich**

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ABSTRACT

One of the main tasks of the government's current efforts to further deepen economic reforms is the successful integration of the Republic of Uzbekistan into the international trade system. Accession to the World Trade Organization will contribute to accelerating this integration and create opportunities for the country to access foreign markets in the most favorable ways.

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One of the most pressing issues in the foreign economic policy of our Republic is to become a full member of the World Trade Organization — the only international organization responsible for regulating trade and exchange relations between different countries. Naturally, accession to this trade organization requires a thorough study of the mechanisms for forming customs duties and the factors influencing them, as well as the introduction of several adjustments to the customs payment system.

It should be noted that customs duties serve as a significant source of revenue for countries. Each state may adjust or abolish customs duty rates based on the needs of its population; the main objective of such measures is to strike a balance between supporting economic activity and ensuring sufficient budget revenues.

It should be particularly emphasized that import customs duties represent one of the key components of collected customs payments. Therefore, analyzing and continuously studying the factors that influence the collectability of import customs duties is of great relevance and importance.

The results of our scientific research, based on the analysis of practical data, indicate that several factors may influence the amount and collectability of import customs duties. The rational use of these factors contributes to exceeding projected targets for import customs revenue, achieving the set objectives, and ensuring a positive impact on the formation of state budget revenues.

If we analyze the amount of import customs duties transferred to the revenue part of the State Budget by the customs authorities of our Republic during 2019–2023, it can be observed that in 2019 the collected import customs duties amounted to 2,312.6 billion UZS, in 2020 —

3,553.7 billion UZS, in 2021 — 4,764.9 billion UZS, in 2022 — 5,745.7 billion UZS, and in 2023 — 9,606.1 billion UZS. Over these years, the total growth in import customs duties reached 4.1 times (Table 1).

Table 1

Analysis of Changes in Import Customs Duties Transferred by Customs Authorities to the State Budget Revenues and Their Share in the Structure of Customs Payments

№	Indicators	Years				
		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1.	Import customs duties transferred to the State Budget, billion UZS.	2 312,6	3 553,7	4 764,9	5745,7	9606,1
2.	Share of import customs duties in the structure of total customs payments transferred to the State Budget, %.	13,5	14,6	16,1	12,5	16,0

Source: Developed by the Author Based on Data from the Customs Committee

According to the results of our analysis, the share of import customs duties in the total customs payments transferred by the customs authorities to the State Budget during 2019–2023 increased by 2.5%.

In our opinion, the factors influencing the amount and collectability of import customs duties can be classified into two groups: (1) **direct factors** — those that have an immediate impact, and (2) **indirect factors** — those that do not directly affect the collection process but still play a significant role. The direct factors include: (a) the commodity code number in the Foreign Economic Activity Commodity Nomenclature (FEACN); (b) the import customs duty rate; (c) the customs value; (d) the quantity of imported goods; (e) the country of origin; (f) exemptions granted on import customs duties; (g) the exchange rate; (h) the country of manufacture; and (i) the year of production, among other factors.

In addition, the factors that indirectly influence the amount and collectability of import customs duties include: (a) the composition of imported goods; (b) the quality of goods; (c) the level of digitalization in the collection of import customs duties; (d) the knowledge and professional competence of customs officers regarding import customs duties; (e) the organization of customs administration; (f) the promotion of customs procedures among participants of foreign economic activity; (g) the degree of development of regulatory documents governing the calculation and collection of import customs duties; (h) the state of collecting import customs duty arrears; (i) the collection of import customs duties granted deferred payment; (j) the application of risk profiles in the collection process; (k) the effectiveness of customs control forms; (l) the level of use of technical control tools; and (m)

the exchange of information on goods with foreign countries, among others. These interrelations can be graphically illustrated as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Factors influencing the amount of import customs duties

Source: Developed by the Author.

Based on the above analysis, the following recommendations are proposed for the effective use of factors influencing import customs duties:

to expand foreign trade relations through accession to international organizations, in particular, to bring the process of joining the World Trade Organization to its logical conclusion;

to conduct multivariate and econometric analyses of factors affecting import customs duties and, based on their results, to develop short-term and long-term forecasts of import customs duty revenues.

In conclusion, the factors determining the collectability of import customs duties in Uzbekistan depend not only on internal economic conditions but also on external economic and political factors, as well as on the international trade system. These factors interact to ensure the efficiency and transparency of customs authorities' activities. It should be emphasized that systematic and continuous analysis of the factors influencing import customs duties, along with timely implementation of appropriate measures, will contribute to an increase in customs revenues to the state budget and the accurate formation of forecast indicators.

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